

Influence of Financial Problem to the Academic Performance of the Grade 11 Students

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Abstract

This study determined the influence of financial problem to the academic performance of grade 11 students of Tuyom Senior High School as basis for a recommendation. The study combined a quantitative, non-experimental design with a descriptive-correlational technique. The questionnaire is made by the researchers and undergoes a pilot run that is validated by a statistical expert. Researchers used universal sampling where in all grade 11 students of Tuyom Senior High School are chosen as their respondents with a total number of 111 students. Data were analyzed using frequency & percentage, weighted mean, and Pearson r. The result shows that most of the respondents belong to poor family and member of 4P's and there are still many that are not member of any government financial aid programs. The result also showed that some of the indicators such as: only one of their parents are employed, unemployment of their parents made them worry, spending too much money and overspending that hinders them to buy things they needed in school has a significant influence on their academic performance and most of the indicator has a little influence only. Overall, the results showed that the null hypothesis is accepted, thus, there is no significant relationship between financial problem and academic performance. Researchers recommends to the future researcher to explore more about this study, involve the grade 12 students to help the school identify if their student's academic performance are influenced by their financial problem.

Keywords: *Financial Problem, Academic Performance, Descriptive-Correlational, Grade 11 Students, Tuyom Senior High School*

Introduction

A financial problem is a situation in which you are not able to meet your bills on time or afford necessary basic needs. According to the book of Education Policy, academic Performance is the measurement of student achievement across various academic subjects. Teachers and education officials typically measure achievement using classroom performance, graduation rates, and results from standardized tests.

Financial problems are a vital issue for everyone, especially students. Most students must struggle to make ends meet as they come from underprivileged families (Norazlan et al., 2020) Student's classroom performance is an important aspect of their journey towards academic success. However, there are some students that may fail in its academic performance just because he/she is more concentrated on how much money to spend or how muc to save depending on their subjects or projects (Windener, 2018). They are worried in where they are going to get the money to pay for supplies and daily need for a student in school because of their limited budget or resources (Cruz, 2021). Acang et al., (2019) also added that students with families of a low financial status have experienced shortage of resources of money could potentially and negatively affect the student's academic performance. This evidence showcased that financial problem influence student's academic performance.

Financial status is the mix of monetary and economic proportion of an individual's work and the financial and social situation of an individual or family association with others for the reason of salary, work position and work-related status. The responsibility of giving the needs of most students lies on the parents. According to Lukeman (2001), students in a low financial status family tend to have more challenges and difficulty because it doesn't just influence their academic performance, it also affects how they adjust or be competent against students who is better or worse position compared to them. Shifeng et al., (2020) also stated that according to their study, students from a disadvantageous family negatively affecting student's classroom performance.

From the study abroad, specifically in Malaysia by Norazlan & Al-Majdhoud (2020), they discovered that there's significant relationship between financial problems and academic performance of the students. A study in the Philippines by Moore et al., (2021), stated that financial stress impedes their ability to succeed academically and students experiencing financial stress finds it challenging to navigate relationship with wealthier peers, often leading feeling of isolation and embarrassment. In local study in Cebu City Don Carlos A. Gothong Memorial National High School C. Padilla St., Cebu City by Abellana et al., (2020), they discovered that financial problem surely affects the student's performance in school and also their mental and physical aspect. This study proved that financial problem affects students not only here in Cebu and Philippines but also in the other country.

Furthermore, the school of Tuyom Senior High School doesn't have any existing study about this issue about financial problem affecting academic performance, since other school globally discovered that their students' academic performance are influenced by their financial problem, it gives us the urge to study if the academic performance of the student of Tuyom Senior High School is affected by their financial problems. Thus, this study aims to determine if the financial problem influence the academic performance of the grade 11 students not only in the other schools/universities but also here in our school and can make recommendations to help students.

Literature Review

Financial Problem

According to Archuleta, Dale & Spann (2013), the impact of financial concerns on overall mental health has become a popular topic among researchers and practitioners. In this exploratory study, possible associations of financial anxiety were explored using a sample of 180 college students who sought services at a university peer financial counseling center in a Midwestern state. Of particular interest was the influence of debt on student financial anxiety. To measure financial anxiety, a new scale was developed, the Financial Anxiety Scale (FAS), that can be used as a tool for financial planners, counselors, and educators to identify individuals who are experiencing increased levels of financial distress that may call for a referral to an appropriate professional. Results from two hierarchical regressions indicated that financial satisfaction, student loans, and gender are associated with financial anxiety. Path-analyses showed that levels of daily financial stress were associated with individuals' perceptions of manageability and internal control regarding their financial situation. These factors, in turn, directly influenced the students' levels of psychological well-being. In contrast, chronic financial strain was shown to influence students' psychological well-being by negatively affecting the degree of comprehensibility regarding their situation as well as their senses of control and self-esteem. These findings were taken to indicate the necessity of differentiating between sources of financial distress (immediate or ongoing) when attempting to understand, and mitigate, the effects of university students' financial situation.

According to Nnamani, Dikko and Kinta (2014), they mentioned that financial problems of the students extremely contribute to the student's low academic performance, which therefore leads to the low quality of education in many ways. Financial problem meet's the daily needs of the students when it comes to their projects, research, and other homework that involves money, in addition, students may feel stress on how they can solve this financial problem that is significant for their daily needs as a student (Dand and Balus, 2015).

These are related to the Financial Problem Affecting Students Academic Performance, it stated that those people who experience high level of financial distress can lead to Financial Anxiety that can also affect to student's academic performance because it can make them lack of focus to the teacher's discussion, it has a big impact to their academic performances of the students who experience this financial problem.

Classroom Performance

This was conducted to examine different factors influencing the academic performance of students. This also examined the learning methods used by students and how these affected their academic scores (Dand and Balus, 2025). The students' cumulative Grade Point Average (GPA) was used as a measure of classroom performance. The data were analyzed quantitatively, and the results showed that factors such as gender, nationality of student, co-curricular activities and an interest in pursuing higher degrees affected students' academic scores. The use of past year examination papers as a learning method improved students' academic scores compared to other methods.

In connection with this, Shtag and Khan (2012) stated that this are carried out to investigate factors affecting students' performance. The focus of this research is that student performance in intermediate examination is linked with students' outline consisted of his approach towards communication, learning facilities, proper guidance, and family stress. This is based on student profile developed on the bases of information and data collected through assessment from students of a group of private colleges.

There is differential effectiveness in learning and teaching methods for the effective learning to happen for their students that has significant impact to their classroom performance that can affect to their academic scores. By balancing between works and academics, some students must struggle to overcome and manage their financial problems (Zhou et., al, 2020).

This affects their academic performance as they must divide their time in focusing and attention between work and studies and those students who experience financially stressed have lower grades and are more likely to drop out.

Parents Unemployment

Unemployment of both parents negatively influenced self-rated health of both genders and long-term well-being of females. After including parental education and financial strain in the model, the negative effect of father's and mother's long-term unemployment on health remained significant. However, influence of unemployment of both parents on health disappeared after adjusting for these variables. To explore the associations between mother's and father's employment status separately and together and the subjective health of children; and how parental education and financial strain can modify these associations.

Lower parental earnings limit parents' opportunities for financial support and children's access to material resources. There is some empirical evidence supporting the assumption that negative intergenerational effects are at least partially related to a family's reduced economic resources (Lehte, Erola & KORHALA, 2019).

It has a big impact to their children's if they have this family problem that can cause stress to their children's that made them unfocused to their class that may lead to lower grades.

Organization of the Government

According to Federal (2013), the US Department of Education was created in 1867 to collect information on schools and teaching that would help the states establish effective school systems. While the agency's name and location within the executive branch have changed over the past 130 years.

Tabuga, Mina & Reyes (2013) stated that year 2013 marks the fifth year of the Pantawid Pamilyang Pilipino Program (4Ps) implementation in the country since its inception in 2008. The first batch of beneficiaries will be graduating from the program in several times. Meanwhile, the government continues to expand the implementation, devising along the way, several variants that it deems necessary to address the many facets of poverty. The 4Ps is by far the largest poverty reduction and social development program the Philippine government has ever conceived. Approximately 120 billion pesos have already been allocated to the program up to 2013. The program's dual objectives are social assistance and social development. It provides cash assistance to poor families to alleviate their immediate needs and aims to "break the intergenerational poverty cycle through investments in human capital." As program graduation nears, many questions arise of what to expect of this program. It is rather fitting at this point to draw together assessments that have been conducted so far and to look into some important issues in terms of design and implementation. The paper seeks to answer whether expanding the program would likely yield better results or not. It discusses the outstanding issues most especially those on the aspects that have a bearing on the program's ability to facilitate inclusive growth.

This literature says that organization of the government like 4Ps can help students in their school expenses that will make them avoid stress made by the financial problem.

Financial Problem Affecting Students' Classroom Performance

Financial plays an important role in students' academic performance. Financial problems are a serious issue that needs to be addressed as it leads to multiple stages of problems such as health issues and academic performance. Dang and Bulus (2015) education is a high-cost social service therefore insufficient financial support will be a problem for students to enhance themselves in academics thus leading to poor academic performance. This paper aims to identify the relationship between financial problems and academic performance faced by public university students in Malaysia. Self-administered surveys were used to gather data from a total of 120 respondents among public university students. Data collected were analyzed using the SPSS to obtain the descriptive statistics. From the results, there is a significant relationship between financial problems and academic performance indicating that the students with financial problems affect their academic performance (Norazlan, Yusut & Majdhouh, 2020).

Financial problem is a situation where money worries are causing stress. However, college student has been facing financial problem lately and this problem had become a major problem for college student. Financial problem faced by student are known as they do not have enough money for their daily expenses, where money worries is causing them to stress. After that, financial problems will bring impact to both mental and physical health. According to Halliday Wynes, (2014), a student financial position will affect their commitment in learning which will affect their academic performance.

Related Studies

The following are studies from online sources that can help in analyzing of some information that are connected to this study.

Financial Problem of the Students

Based on the study of Hossain, et al., (2022), practical implications Results indicate that financial stress has a strong impact on participation in different academic and personal activities of a student. Therefore, parents, university administration and student counselor should consider the factor to assess stress of a student. Additionally, Wynes (2014) also stated that a student financial position will affect their commitment in learning which will affect their academic performance.

In connection with this, Borinaga, et.al (2023) discover that the attainment of financial contentment significantly influences the classroom performance of college students. As students' progress through their academic pursuits, the presence of financial concerns and limitations frequently gives rise to stress and distractions that impede their capacity to focus on their studies. Hence, it is crucial to analyze the correlation between financial contentment and scholastic accomplishment to ascertain the elements that contribute to the academic triumph of students.

This study says that financial problem can cause stress to the students and the presence of financial concerns and limitations frequently gives rise to stress and distractions that impede their capacity to focus on their studies.

Financial Problem of Students in Terms of Unemployment of Parents

One of the factors that causes the students to have financial problem is having unemployed parents. Research showing how this comes about indicates that children living with parents out of work tend to live in poorer physical conditions at home and are less likely to access the educational goods and services that stimulate skill acquisition and development (Haveman, Wolfe and Spaulding, 1991; Ferreira and Schady, 2009; Kalil and Wightman, 2009), which in turn predicts worse educational outcomes.

Parental unemployment is also associated with parental stress and ineffective parenting behavior that can worsen family dynamics and negatively affect children's subsequent outcomes. The family stress model (Conger and Elder, 1994), for example, argues that parental job loss puts parents under emotional strain, which increases chances of family discord and marital dissolution, inhibits parental emotional warmth, decreases the quality of family relationships, and leads to poor learning environments. This, in turn, can lead to poor behavioral adjustment and low levels of educational attainment in children (Brand, 2015). Expect parental job loss to be negatively associated with children's educational achievements.

Parents unemployment leads financial problem because they don't have a stable source of income. Senior high school needs enough money to spend for their transportation, foods, and school expenses, and it made them stress in thinking of where to get money because they can't always rely on their parents due to unemployment.

Academic Performance of Students

Academic performance depends on classroom interaction and academic interaction depends on study habits and home environment. It means academic performance can be estimated for any student by its home environment and learning skills and by its classroom interaction, study habits, and home environment. By examining the three possible paths of estimating classroom performance, the strongest path is the home environment which affects the learning skills and ultimately learning skills lead to affect the academic performance. According to our model students can achieve high academic performance by focus on home environment and learning skills (Shahzadi and Ahmad, 2011).

Academic performance depends on interaction, if students are stress, they can't interact positively due to overthinking of their problem. And some students that can't afford what their classmates can has a big possibility of being bullied that leads them to avoid interacting in their classrooms.

Classroom Performance of Students Base on Attendance

According to the study of Ancheta et. al. (2021), the mark and absence of the students have negative inverse correlation. It means that as the absence of the student increases, the mark also decreases of at least 1 mark. It is concluded that students' class attendance is very critical in terms of learning as it affects students' achievement.

In addition, as stated in the study of Ancheta, Daniel, & Ahmad, 2021, Student attendance is one of the issues that most teachers in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) is facing today. Many colleges and universities have compulsory attendance policies while others have refrain from making it as such. Despite the different policies, higher education teachers believe that attendance has positive effect in academic performance. Non-attendance in class lecture is seen as one of the reasons for academic failure.

Student's Classroom Performance Base on Their School Grade

This study examined classroom assessment practice of 3rd-through 12th-grade teachers in a Midwestern state. In addition to determining the frequency with which specific assessment item formats were utilized, the level of use of selected "best practice" approaches to assessment was considered (performance-based assessment, teachers-made tests, and formative assessment). Essays and written assignments were the most common assessment format. Female teachers choose performance-based assessment and used much more frequently by language arts teachers than by those who teach other subjects and is more common at higher levels than at the elementary level. Though teachers design their own classroom assessment, they routinely rely on test or items written by others. Formative assessment is not common, as only about 12% of assessment do not affect student grades and 3 out of 4 assessments are administered after instruction is completed. Implications for promoting quality classroom assessment are discussed.

Attendance of the students is very important aspects in their classroom performance, if they have many absences then there is a big possibility that they can gain a small grade that can affect their classroom performance. It also says that some of the reasons of their absences are self-financing, and hours worked on jobs that means they are the one who are working for their own needs. This means that financial problem influenced student's attendance.

Significant Relationship Between Financial Problem to the Classroom

Performance of the Students

From the study of Alegre et. al. (2020), that currently some students are struggling with school expenses, and another problem for students is lack of school equipment. and added two more years for senior high school, and those students who want to work students, but underage can't work because they are underage, and their parents can't afford to educate their child due to a disability on financial support. and if other students lack the financial support, they will be less educated. Nowadays it is difficult to make money for school supplies, food, supplies, and more (2020).

Research Methods

This research combined a quantitative, non-experimental design with a descriptive-correlational technique. Quantitative research rigorous, objective, systematic process for obtaining information about variables using numerical data. It used to define and investigate relationship between variables (Lama, 2005). Correlational research is quantitative research method in which two or more quantitative variable from the same set of individuals or compared. This design employed since the primary goal of the research is to investigate the influence of financial problem to the academic performance of grade 11 students.

Results and Findings

As to the demographic profile of the respondents, most of them were having below Php10,957 and most of them were member of 4P's but there are still a lot of them (37% from the total population) are not a member of any livelihood/organization of the Government.

As to the extent that the Financial Problem affects the classroom performance of the respondents, only one parent was employed and being worry due to unemployment of their parents has a significant influence to their academic performance. According to them, unemployment of their parents making them stress, overthink, and feel hopeless has a little influence to their academic performance. Respondents also respond that, too much usage of their money that hinders them to buy things they needed for school has a significant influence to their academic performance while, spending their money though it's not needed, buying too many things, and overspending that made them stress specially in times that they had unexpected expenses in school has little influence to their academic performance.

As to the level of academic performance of the respondent base on their school grades, result showed that, most of them got 90-100 grade during their 1st semester and a lot of them has 85-89 grade (42% of the population).

As to the significant relationship, the result showed that there was a very low negative correlation between financial problem of the students to their academic performance that means, this study accepted the null hypothesis which was no significant relationship between financial problem and academic performance of the students.

Recommendations

1. Conduct a study in connection with this study every year. This includes determining if the academic performances of next grade 11 students are affected by their financial problem.
2. Grade 12 students have a lot of expenses too and researchers recommend that the future researcher will conduct a similar study involving grade 12 students of Tuyom Senior High School.
3. Parents are recommended to monitor their students/children if their academic performance are affected by their financial problem.
4. Researchers recommended that teachers must also check if their students is problematic so that they can help them financially.
5. Government are recommended to have a proper survey if all unprivileged students are a provided by their financial assistance.
6. School is recommended to have a activity where students will take a break from their academic and problems.
7. Teachers are recommended to give students project where they don't need to spend a lot of money.

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